

A REVIEW ON PRECISION AGRICULTURE FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVING

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ABSTRACT

Precision agriculture exploits the advances in technology to address the issues of crop productivity and quality in a shorter time with minimal human intervention which results in sustainable farming and improved economic status of the farmers. Switching to precision agriculture entirely or at least partly could offer a humongous advantage to the farmers as well as the consumers. Precision agriculture is a concept of farm management incorporating technology for improved efficiency. The amalgamation of the technologies like Global Positioning System, satellite and aerial imaging, Internet of Things, sensors, Wi-Fi, Robots, Drones, Nano Technology and Artificial Intelligence with farming can greatly improve the yield, reduce losses, decrease pesticide load without the indiscriminate use of fertilizers and the wastage of water. In spite of the multiple benefits that Precision agriculture proffers, majority of the farm owners hesitate to execute the same considering the considerable capital investment and the lack of technological knowledge. In extensive crop canopies, the advantages offered by automating the agricultural process, supersede the capital expenditure incurred in purchasing the state-of-the-art equipment.

INDEXTERMS—Precision Agriculture, Internet of Things, Machine Learning, Agricultural Robots, Government Initiatives, Geographical Information System, Sustainable India

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is a major part of the economy in India. With 179.9 million hectares of agricultural land, India holds the second largest agricultural land after China. India also ranks as the second largest food producing country on a global scale with the agricultural sector accounting for 13.7% of the GDP. 58% of the Indians are based on farming for their livelihood. According to the Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Department of Agriculture, Cooperation and Farmers Ministry of Agriculture and Farmer's Welfare, Government of India, the Rate of Gross Capital Formation to GDP at current prices is 32.2% [1].

Since the Independence, Indian government has actively taken up initiatives like the Green Revolution which lead to increase in food production by 4 times. However, because inefficient post – harvest regulations, India is ranked as 102 as per Global Hunger Index (GHI) during the year 2019 [2]. The post harvest loss in India is 40% as compared to 33% on a global scale. This amounts to a loss of whopping Rs.92,651 crores per annum. The farmer death rate in India has been increasing consistently due to the use of lethal pesticides like Monocrotophos, Triazophos Phosphamidion, Phorate, Methomyl, etc... which are highly toxic to the farmers. The pesticide overload on crops due to the lack of regulations on the quantity of pesticides applied and the want of awareness among farmers on the pesticide management has lead to the production of inferior quality food. Excessive indiscriminate use of chemical fertilizers to over supplement the soil with Nitrogen, Phosphorous and Potassium will harm the soil health in the long run and also pollute the surrounding air and water bodies. Organic fertilizers have limited availability and burdensome to an average farmer due their high price.

Most farmers use conventional ways for their farming from the preparation of soil prior to the sowing of seeds to the harvesting of crop and post-harvest management. Precision agriculture or satellite farming is a concept of farm management which involves the use of technology to assist the farmer in every phase of farming. The access to technologies like Satellite imagery, Satellite navigation, drones, robots, Artificial Intelligence, Machine learning, wi-fi, Internet of Things, multispectral cameras, real time sensors, microcontrollers, etc... can greatly to improve the yield, reduce losses and produce a superior quality crop in an environmentally sustainable way. The inputs to crop like water, soil nutrition enhancers and pesticides can be optimized by variable rate applications. Micro irrigation, green house farming, crop mechanization and crop residue management can be handled by precision agriculture. This paper reviews the various technologies that can be applied to agriculture for a sustainable India.

REVIEW

A. Application of technology at various Stages of farming

Measuring soil Nutrition

Soil health is a very intricate combination of various macro and micronutrients and has to be carefully refined overtime. Soils generally demonstrate inhomogeneous physical, chemical and biological attributes. Soil fertility is determined by the composition of principal nutrients such as nitrogen, potassium, magnesium, phosphorous and calcium and trace metallic nutrients like iron and manganese. Additionally, the amount of humus and the pH value of the soil play a very significant role in soil fertility. The customary, homogeneous fertilization of the agricultural lands usually causes overdosing which in turn results in exposure of the surface and groundwater to the chemicals in fertilizers.

Site-specific plant production is an excellent solution to this situation wherein the spatial inhomogeneities in a particular field are recorded and appropriate action is taken. This necessitates the spatially variable information to be acquired and analysed in a quick and cost efficient manner [3]. Geoelectrical, gamma ray, potentiometric pH and spectral-optical sensors are more economical, efficient and accurate as opposed to the traditional sampling and lab testing for soil nutrients [4] [5].

Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS) is a more sophisticated and accurate technology for in-field determination of soil elements. LIBS is a spectroscopy technique which uses extremely narrow pulses of intense laser radiation onto the soil sample creating a microplasma. The plasma consequently excites the atomic ions emitting radiation particular to the soil sample elemental composition, making simultaneous multi-element analysis possible [6] [7].

PLOUGHING

Unmanned or driverless autonomous tractors for ploughing the fields are available with standardized features with satellite navigation support integrated with computer vision and artificial intelligence for obstacle detection and night time operation [8]. Tractors can be equipped with Digital Throttle Gear Optimizer (DTGO) for efficient fuel usage and digital slipmeters can protect the tractors in slip zones.

WEED REMOVAL

Weeds compete with the crop for moisture and nutrients from the soil. Weeds affect crop yield, attract or harbour detrimental insects and plant pathogens. Many weeds are wind-pollinated and generate copious amounts of pollen which may cause hay fever.

Proper weed control management is vital to a profitable crop production and automation of weed management is the best solution. In conventional weed control systems involve herbicides being sprayed uniformly all over the fields. Apart from the damaging consequences on the main crop, soil and underground water, huge amount of herbicides are wasted as only some parts of fields are covered with weeds.

Growing public concern about herbicides in food, health of farm worker, biodiversity, and the environment have renewed interest in smart weed control measures.

Fig. 1. CO₂ LASER for Weed Removal

Autonomous Drones fitted with a camera can be employed to capture images of every small section of the field. Image processing techniques i.e., morphological operations such as applying dilation followed by erosion method on the images, integrated with deep learning techniques can be applied for weed recognition. The detected weeds can be controlled by annihilating the stem using a CO₂ LASER attached to the drone as shown in Figure 1. The LASER beam should be focussed on the lowest portion of the stem for effective weed mitigation [9].

A laser beam directed towards weeds can be an efficient weed control method as an alternative to herbicides. Lasers may deliver high-density energy to selected plant material, raising the temperature of the water in the plant cells and thereby stop or delay the growth.

Additionally, Weed removal during the crop growth season is also possible with robotic arms which traverse along the passages between the plant rows and pluck them out on both sides [10]. Another technique to kill weeds effectively without affecting the adjacent main crop is to identify weeds from crop images using deep learning algorithms and selectively sprinkle herbicides by correlating the weed coordinates with the geographical coordinates using a GPS navigated Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) [11].

SOWING OF SEEDS

One of the most predominant periods of the crop growing season is the seeding window. The placement and depth of the seed is very critical for a uniform germination and crop maturity. The access to Seed hybrid technologies to pair seed attributes to soil traits, Seed treatments like Solid Matrix Priming (SMP) to induce weed and pest resistance abilities and seed microbes for dosing the seeds with beneficial microbes to minimize fertilizer requirements can make remarkable improvements to the crop growth and yield [12]. Satellite data can be utilized for optimal seed placement, precise application of fertilizer, comprehend field variability and real-time images to measure crop biomass [13]. Sensors can be employed to prevent overlap of seeds, maintain seed depth and monitor emergence.

WATERING (SPRINKLING)

Water scarcity is one of the most significant stumbling blocks in India compelling us to come up with innovative techniques to minimize water usage without compromising the crop yield. Precision irrigation saves precious resources ensuring soil moisture sufficiency with usage of sensors in the fields. Precision irrigation includes soil moisture analysis and notifying farmers of predicted droughts or floods in order to equip them with genuine knowledge in advance [14]. Additionally, it also supplies weather predictions to schedule the farming tasks in the most optimal way. Farmers need not irrigate or fertilize when there is a forecast of rain. This will greatly save resources and prevent pesticides from being washed off the plants. Crop monitoring can also be done from any remote location via cell phone with the assistance of IoT. Crop monitoring systems provide the farmers with precipitation and weather charts, based on which decisions concerning irrigation can be taken.

CROP GROWTH MONITORING AND ESTIMATION

Crop development variations can be represented on a spatial and temporal scale using remote sensing with the help of multispectral and hyperspectral satellite images. The images depict the crop growth, biomass, leaf area index, photosynthetic active radiation, surface temperature, Perpendicular Crop Enhancement Index (PCEI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (ENDVI), precise value of evapotranspiration among others [15] [16]. Analysis reports on these images can be prepared and supplied to the farmer along with suggestions on course of action.

SELECTIVE APPLICATION OF FERTILIZERS USING DRONES

The traditional mode of manual sprinkling of fertilizers, pesticides or any other chemicals may lead to long term pulmonary and dermatological disorders like asthma, leukemia, psoriasis or terminal diseases like cancer. Modern technology has made autonomous spraying of fertilizers and crop monitoring using drones [17]. Moreover, drones provide the additional benefit of swift maneuverability through any terrain with the help of GPS navigation, selective spraying capability, fertilizer quantity control, night vision and speedy coverage of the entire field. Drones can be fitted with universal sprayers and global nozzles for both liquid and solid fertilizers. The same drone can be used for applying pesticides or herbicides.

PEST DETECTION AND CONTROL

Localised temperature surge is an absolute biomarker for the onset of plant disease. Therefore, Thermal infrared imaging can be applied in Precision agriculture to remotely monitor and diagnose the plant health. It can precisely locate the spatial inhomogeneities in the organic composition of the plant leaves non-invasively. Thermographic cameras usually detect radiation in the far-infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum (8 to 12 μm) and produce images called thermograms. Infrared Thermography gives false color images, the pixel color is indicative of the temperature in that region [18]. By the use of thermal infrared imaging, human eye's observation range is extended to the infrared spectral region, which greatly improves the human eye observation sensitivity. Infrared thermographic detection study of plant health can ascertain leaf moisture and physiological stress conditions, and also can be potentially used to diagnose leaf scorch. Thermal imaging can also be replaced by multispectral imaging or hyperspectral imaging all of which offer the benefits of high precision, intuitive images, improved range of detection and night vision causing early diagnosis of crop disease. Multispectral imaging can be applied in Precision agriculture to remotely monitor and diagnose the plant health. It can precisely locate the spatial inhomogeneities in the organic composition of the plant leaves non-invasively. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is an index of plant "greenness" or photosynthetic activity, and is one of the most commonly used vegetation indices [19]. Photosynthetically active vegetation absorbs most of the red light which hits it while reflecting much of the near infrared light. Vegetation which is dead or stressed reflects more red light and less near infrared light.

Multispectral sensing imaging technology use Green, Red, Red-Edge and Near Infrared wavebands to capture both visible and invisible images of crops and vegetation. By the use of Multispectral imaging, human eye's observation range is extended to the infrared spectral region, which greatly improves the human eye observation sensitivity. Multispectral study of plant health can ascertain leaf moisture and physiological stress conditions, and also can be potentially used to diagnose leaf scorch.

Fig. 2. Drones with Multispectral Camera for Pest Identification and Localized Pesticide Sprinkling

Drones fixed with thermal infrared imaging camera can be flown over an agricultural land to collect thermal imaging video data. The drone can also be interfaced with a high precision GPS module for its navigation according to a predetermined path to cover the entire farm keeping within the geographical boundaries of the farm as shown in Figure 2.

YIELD ESTIMATION

Researchers have proposed very powerful scientific models for crop yield estimation like the Monteith's model which calculates Photosynthetically Active Radiation, Stanford's model which determines the efficiency with which light is

used and the Surface Energy Balance Algorithm for Land which provides time-space variation in land wetness [20] [21] [22]. All these models can accurately determine the available biomass even in the event of satellite data outage.

HARVESTING

Harvesting is highly a monotonous job and heavily taxing to the farmer. It requires dexterity, patience and gentleness on the farmer's part to harvest the produce in order not to bruise the fruits and vegetables or tear the leafy greens. Robots are an excellent alternative for picking fruits, vegetables as well as harvesting and threshing food grains. Robots can be integrated with computer vision and machine learning in order to train them to distinguish between ripe and unripe produce [23]. Harvesting robots are definitely much faster and more efficient than humans. Robotic agricultural equipment rely on GPS for their navigation and can use radio transmission to send updates on the harvest to the remote user.

SEGREGATION OF DEFECTIVE PRODUCE FROM GOOD QUALITY PRODUCE

Sorting of produce ensures that the best quality food reaches the consumer. An exclusive technology, Harvest Quality Vision (HQV) uses computer vision that scans the produce via a camera attachment and fabricates a 3D model of the scanned fruit or vegetable which are further analyzed to measure the size, determine the color profile, and assess the quantity of the consignment scanned within moments [24]. HQV technology helps in the sorting of the fruits or vegetables into the appropriate bins based on their size effortlessly with negligible damage to the produce.

POST HARVEST MANAGEMENT

The globalization of food trade over the past two decades has resulted in an increased distance of the produce travelling from the farm to the consumer. The global food export has raised many folds resulting in food wastage and contamination during transport, especially of perishable produce like fruits and vegetables. Consequently, it is a significant challenge to keep up the quality and safety of the produce without increasing the cost component. Minimizing post harvest wastage has a direct positive impact on poverty alleviation, employment generation, sustainable living, nutrition and safety. Pre cooling of the produce can greatly reduce food wastage and contamination ensuring its longer shelf life. Intelligent temperature controlled pre-cooling systems like cool bots can replace refrigerators which emit greenhouse gases and are environmentally destructive [25].

Food contamination can be substantially reduced through environment friendly packaging material during storage and transport. Bio-nanocomposites and bio-polymers offer sufficient mechanical durability to replace the ubiquitous toxic plastic packaging material.

Innovative packaging technology like Time temperature indicator (TTI) with intelligent packaging equipment supplies the consumer with reliable and accurate information on the quality, freshness and safety of the food. Intelligent packaging may include sensors mimicking olfactory receptors, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) systems, sensors to measure temperature, humidity, light exposure, pH sensors, etc to monitor the integrity of packaging and quality of food [26].

Amorphous silicium photovoltaic cells, carbon nanotubes and electronic temperature tracking sensor can be fabricated by flexible printing and integrated with the packaging material to monitor the perishable goods and differentiate vapours and gases at parts per million.

Tracking of farm produce shipments can be carried out effectively with web-based systems for storage, analysis, transfer and availability of data to achieve complete traceability. Warehouse maintenance and inventory records can be computerized for significant improvement in quantitative and qualitative data logging.

MISCELLANEOUS

Indoor Farming

Indoor agriculture can also be completely automated with the use of sensors and robots controlled via a cloud for efficient supervision. These automated mini farms can produce much higher yields incorporating hydroponic and vertical farming using 90% less water than conventional farms [27].

AVIAN INTRUDERS

Birds are a serious nuisance as they pillage the crop and cause heavy losses to the farmer. High-tech devices equipped with microprocessors, motion sensors, surveillance cameras and intruder detection algorithms involving machine learning can be used to keep the pesky birds at bay. Prerecorded gun shots or predatory screams can be played or water cannons can be fired upon detection of bird flocks to scare them away [28]. These electronic scarecrows can be solar powered for sustainability

FARM FIRES

Fires in farms can cause large scale devastation if not extinguished immediately. Intelligent temperature and fire sensors can be employed to detect the onset of a farm fire and turn on microcontroller based fire extinguishing systems for localized fire control. Events of fire can be transmitted as alarm signals to the farmer.

NATURAL DISASTERS

Natural disasters like floods, famines, cyclones and earthquakes can be forecasted and disseminated to the farmers with suggested recourses using Remote Sensing and Geographical Information System to help salvage the crop to the best of their abilities [29].

DRAWBACKS OF PRECISION AGRICULTURE

Precision agriculture involves high capital investment which will definitely be overcompensated in the due course but is undoubtedly a huge financial burden on the farmer in the initial stages. Operation of technologically advanced equipment, collecting and analysing huge amounts of data and equipment maintenance requires basic knowledge and training which is not accessible to an average farmer in India. Precision agriculture uses network connected technologies, communication systems, data analytics, remote sensing and satellite navigation. Although, these technologies assist in farm and livestock management with utmost accuracy to reduce long term operation costs and improve the quality and quantity of yield, there is a heightened threat of exposure to cyber hacking [30]. The system is vulnerable to malicious cyber attacks like theft of data and physical resources, leakage of confidential information, equipment destruction, and reputation damage by competitors. Land fragmentation is a significant hurdle in the implementation of large scale autonomous farming but most farmers own small pieces of land.

INDIAN GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES TO ADOPT AND PROMOTE PRECISION FARMING

Precision Agriculture for Development (PAD) is India's initiative since 2016 to provide access to customized and validated advisory content regarding Precision Agriculture to the farmers. In September 2020, in excess of 1 million farmers were benefitted through this service. PAD establishes a two way communication between the farmers and PAD personnel to refine the advisory content and improve the services and dissemination of vital information [31].

Working Groups (WGs) of India-US Knowledge Initiative on Agriculture (KIA) has identified Precision Agriculture as a thrust area. National Agricultural Innovation Project (NAIP) has announced a budget of 285 million dollars for innovations in agricultural technology. Currently there are 17 Precision Farming Development Centers (PFDCs) scattered all over India for imparting training to a large number of farmers on precision irrigation and provide infrastructure and operational support. Punjab, Haryana and Uttar Pradesh are successfully running Tata Kisan Kendra. Private sector companies have set up around 1200 'e-choupals' across 4 states, equipping farmers with information on market prices, scientific farm practices, weather and crop disease forecasts.

CONCLUSIONS

India is primarily dependent on agriculture for its economy and with the access to innovative technologies like artificial intelligence, robotics, computer vision, satellite navigation, GIS and remote sensing, the mode of agriculture is morphing drastically. Precision agriculture is less labour intensive, improves the quality and quantity of yield as well as environment friendly and sustainable. Technology can be applied in every phase of agriculture for simplifying the farming activities and optimizing the yield. Precision agriculture significantly reduces the carbon footprint, conserves water, preserves and

improves soil fertility, prevents chemical toxicity related diseases in farmers contributing towards a sustainable India. Government initiatives on sensitizing the farmers about precision agriculture such as awareness programs, information dissemination, training, skill development and subsidizing equipment can encourage more farmers to accept and practice precision agriculture. Although the capital investment involved in precision agriculture is high, the benefits to the farmer are manifold and the expenditure can be recovered multiple times over a short span of time.

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